

INTEGRATING UDL AND ADDRESSING ASD-SPECIFIC CHALLENGES IN EFL INSTRUCTION: PERSONAL DEVELOPMENT FOR PRE-SERVICE TEACHERS

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Abstract. *This paper creates a learning environment focused on teaching strategies and approaches to engage students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) in inclusive classroom environments by integrating Universal Design for Learning (UDL). This personal development (PD) series highlights the importance of including students with Autism in classroom interactions rather than isolating them in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classes. It explores how pre-service teachers can be trained to use effective educational strategies and techniques for teaching learners with autism. Based on research on UDL-integrated EFL instruction strategies like structured visual schedules, sensory-friendly zones, interactive social stories, choice boards for communication, and positive reinforcement systems, this paper aims to develop Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) that prepares future educators to support students with Autism in mainstream classrooms. The ultimate goal is to enhance teacher preparedness in creating accessible, engaging, and inclusive learning environments.*

Key words: *Universal Design for Learning (UDL), Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), English as a Foreign Language (EFL), Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK), Personal Development (PD), pre-service teachers.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqola Universal Design for Learning (UDL) yondashuvini integratsiya qilish orqali inkluziv sinf muhitida Autizm spektr buzilishi (ASD) bo'lgan o'quvchilarni ta'lim jarayoniga jalb etishga qaratilgan o'qitish strategiyalari va metodlariga asoslangan ta'lim muhitini yaratishni ko'zda tutadi. Ushbu shaxsiy rivojlanish (PD) dasturi ingliz tilini chet tili sifatida (EFL) o'qitish jarayonida autizmi bor o'quvchilarni izolyatsiya qilish o'rniga ularni sinfdagi o'zaro muloqot jarayonlariga faol qo'shish muhimligini ta'kidlaydi.*

Maqolada bo'lajak o'qituvchilarni autizmi bor o'quvchilarni o'qitishda samarali pedagogik strategiya va texnikalardan foydalanishga qanday tayyorlash mumkinligi yoritiladi. UDL asosida integratsiyalashgan EFL o'qitish strategiyalari, jumladan, tuzilgan vizual jadval

va rejalashtirish, sensor jihatdan qulay hududlar, interaktiv ijtimoiy hikoyalar, muloqot uchun tanlov kartalari hamda ijobiy rag‘batlantirish tizimlari bo‘yicha tadqiqotlarga tayangan holda, maqola kelajak pedagoglarini umumta‘lim sinflarida autizmi bor o‘quvchilarni qo‘llab-quvvatlashga tayyorlaydigan pedagogik mazmun bilimlarini (PCK) rivojlantirishni maqsad qiladi. Yakuniy maqsad — o‘qituvchilarning ochiq, qamrovli va qiziqarli ta‘lim muhitini yaratish bo‘yicha tayyorgarligini kuchaytirishdir.

Kalit so‘zlar: *Universal Design for Learning (UDL), Autizm spektr buzilishi (ASD), Ingliz tili chet tili sifatida (EFL), Pedagogik mazmun bilimlari (PCK), Shaxsiy rivojlanish (PD), bo‘lajak o‘qituvchilar.*

Introduction.

This study focuses on teaching neurodiverse learners, particularly students with autism. The aim of this project is to create EFL activities for developing language, literacy, and communication skills in an inclusive space while addressing the unique sensory and social needs of students with ASD. Concerning the subject specificity, the suggested activities are not for EFL classes only, but also can be tailored to other subjects, and the designed strategies can be universally applicable across all subjects. To make this research’s direction clearer, the primary goal has been identified to help pre-service teachers become aware of autism spectrum disorder and develop pedagogical content knowledge (PCK). A series of research shows that pre-service teachers have limited knowledge of ASD and adapting UDL for EFL. To cater to this research gap, these novice teachers will find the suggested professional development training incorporating ASD-focused lesson plans helpful. The overall gap shows that future teachers who have been trained in teacher preparation programs find managing the sensory needs of ASD students and facilitating social collaboration challenging. For this reason, the suggested PCK through this paper ensures that the participants learn how to teach neurodiverse learners and adjust their teaching practices to inclusive education for students with autism.

The significance of this project is to help pre-service teachers understand some key points of integrating UDL in their mainstream classes while they are teaching neurodiverse students, including those with autism. This research is important because, firstly, some teachers may have limited or no knowledge of autism, especially novice teachers and those new to the classroom. When they are exposed to students with autism, they might be lost, not fully understanding the sensory or communication challenges these students might face in their classroom. The second challenge that teachers should be ready to address is adapting teaching strategies, as pre-service teachers need to learn how to adapt standard teaching strategies to accommodate and deal with students' diverse sensory, cognitive, and social needs. Last but not least, another potential difficulty for teachers might be creating inclusive classrooms. This research project attempts to provide solutions to these challenges, offering an EFL learning environment where neurodiverse students feel included without segregating them from their peers. So, the research question for this paper is:

- How can pre-service teachers effectively integrate Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles to support the academic development of students with Autism Spectrum Disorder in inclusive EFL classrooms?

- How can pre-service teachers effectively integrate sensory-friendly strategies to support the social development of students with Autism Spectrum Disorder in inclusive EFL classrooms?

Literature review.

Khurana (2019) discusses that variation, but not homogeneity in learning is a norm which refers to every child that learn differently in the classroom. The realization of learning that is highly individualized and unique, perpetuated Universal Design for Learning (UDL) which ensures equitable access to make an inclusive environment targeting all the learners. One of the significant concepts that has been suggested for applying inclusion in the classroom is UDL. It is an educational framework that that is of great assistance for teachers and instructional designers to plan more effective learning environment which include students with disabilities. CAST (2024) highlights that UDL is an educational framework that helps educators proactively design curricula and educational environments to be efficient for all learners from the start by encouraging a diverse and flexible method the class practices. There are three principles of UDL: multiple means of representation, multiple ways of action and expression, and multiple means of engagement (CAST, 2024), which make the lessons accessible, achievable, and flexible.

Among the five key influences of UDL (social models of disability, technology, universal design, and IDEA '97), neurodiversity is worth mentioning, which has become a controversial topic in the past few decades. This concept has had a great impact in the field of autism (Silberman, 2015). According to Mastropier (2010), children with autism are generally described as having great difficulty communicating and interacting with and responding to other people. Similarly, Apex ABA (n.d.) defines Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) as a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by challenges in social interaction, communication, and repetitive behaviors. Among many defined characteristics, the follow-up features are common for this type of children. Firstly, individuals with autism often experience *sensory sensitivities*, making certain public spaces overwhelming or distressing for them (Apex ABA, n.d.) Many individuals with this disorder also show stereotypic behavior such as self-stimulating behaviors (e.g. rocking, hand-flapping); bizarre speech patterns, such as repeating other people’s words over and over again (echolalia); and disruptive behavior, including self-injury (Hall, 2009, as cited in Mastropier, 2010).

Autism Navigator (2024) points out that we know much more about ASD than we did ten years ago, and although it is still considered a lifelong diagnosis, now we have reached our understanding of the way we define, diagnose, and treat ASD. The signs of ASD are usually apparent in early childhood. The Texas Council for Developmental Disabilities (2024) quotes that individuals in the category of autism are considered to be in the “high functioning range” of the disorder because they can speak and often test to have very high IQs, but social impairments can prove to necessitate a lifetime support. At an early age, educators alongside with parents should diagnose and create an individualized early intervention at school, home and in the whole society. Children with ASD can lead productive, inclusive and fulfilling lives. Many research shows that this kind of children do well in school, take part in activities they enjoy, go to university and even get jobs in their adulthood. For this reason, educators have to seek an *inclusive environment* for such young students, collaborating with parents and professionals.

Mastropier (2010) mentions that children with autism may be diagnosed, indicating that they can function along a continuum of severe to mild disabilities and that educational accommodations may be diverse according to their functional level. The first challenge to meet

these accommodations is *communication barriers*, with which students struggle with verbal communication and may need *visual supports or alternative communication methods*. Zohoorian (2024) et al, notes that even though there has been limited literature throughout the world, reviewed studies showed improvement in learning by suitable and various methods, including representative *visual pictures*.

Pretorius & Botha (2024) offer creating *structured visual schedules*, for each child with autism using images or icons representing daily activities (e.g. snack time) and they demonstrate several reasons such visual schedules might be essential to these children. Firstly, they promote predictability which can help reduce anxiety and children may know what comes next and feel more in control of their environment. Secondly, visual schedules and other picture-based classroom representations accommodate can make communication easier for such children with autism who are pre-verbal or minimally verbal children. Last but not least, such visual aids can make transitions between activities smoother and empower children to take ownership enabling them to complete tasks independently and build like skills. Paro (2024) says that a number of symbols might be used as visual representations including line drawings and abstract images like those from Boardmaker or Smarty Symbols. Next, real pictures of real objects and places can make it easier for those children to understand. Also, she suggests starting with one picture for younger or less experienced children and gradually increase the number of pictures as the child becomes familiar with the task.

It is believed that communication with children with ASD is more comfortable through *assistive technology* which is another accommodation for them to make an effective learning environment. Chamshama and Mnyanyi (2024) point out that interaction of ICT in teaching children with autism from the perceptions elicits positive feelings, meaning the more they interact with ICT facilities, children with ASD become familiar with the behavior of some computer-related programs. As one aspect of inclusion of students with autism is the role of technology, assistive technologies such as communication boards and adaptive devices are crucial in helping students with physical or cognitive limitations. Boardmaker- another tool of communication board is using symbols to aid to communicate, helping students with severe communication barriers. Assistive technology plays a significant role in enhancing the independence and quality of life for individuals with autism (The Treetop, 2024). When creating autism-friendly environment in the classroom, it is essential to consider the integration of remote control for lighting, temperature, and security features. Visual and auditory alert systems assist with daily routines and reminders. Communication aids, such as speech-to-text devices or visual supports, facilitate effective communication for individuals with autism.

Like assistive technology tools, Mastropier (2010) suggests using *Alternative and Augmentative Communication, News-2-U, and BoardMaker* for students with low-incidence disabilities, including autism, who require some adaptations in literacy materials that will aid their ability to communicate. Alternative and Augmentative Communication (ACC) devices are good examples, which are widely available in the range from high-tech to low-tech options. This means that some use very little technology and various others are relying on more complex technological systems for delivery. One alternative and augmentative version of a newspaper that is available is News-2-U. News-2-U is published weekly and it is available for free subscription, which features relevant newsworthy *interactive social stories* printed using visual symbols that represent words. Another tool is BoardMaker, a software program that contains graphics that can be used to develop and design communication displays, which is available online on a weekly

basis. While teachers who opt for News-2-U are most likely one to obtain the software BoardMaker, which can be used to develop a wide range of displays using over 3,000 graphic picture and communication symbols and over 100 templates for calendars, schedules, and other formats. BoardMaker for Windows comes with 19 languages, and it can also be combined with *Speaking Dynamically Pro* to include the speech capabilities. This way, the symbols can be used as overlays and can be heard aloud for students who require hearing the symbols in addition to looking at them. Another tool is *BoardMaker Plus*, which adds sound, voice, animation, and video capabilities to the software. These can be adapted well to the classroom to accommodate the needs of students with disabilities who have speech or hearing challenges to make their classrooms more meaningful and interactive.

The next challenge that should be accommodated is creating *sensory-regulation spaces or sensory-friendly zones* in the classroom because creating a calming environment is essential for individuals with autism. The Treetop (2024) suggests minimizing sensory overload and providing spaces that promote relaxation and comfort to accommodate students with autism. Their design strategies include using neutral colors, providing cozy spaces, and limiting visual distractions. Soft and muted tones help create a soothing atmosphere, incorporating cozy corners or designated areas where individuals can retreat and feel secure. These spaces can be equipped with comfortable seating, cushions, and soft textures. Minimizing clutter and excessive visual stimuli by organizing spaces in a clean and organized manner. Lighting plays a crucial role in creating an autism-friendly environment. Natural light, whenever possible, is generally softer and less harsh than artificial lighting, avoiding fluorescent lighting. It can flicker and emit a buzzing sound that can be bothersome to students with autism.

Another type of accommodation that should be applied to meet students with autism in the new affective learning environment is *using positive reinforcement systems*. This reinforcement can be applied to aid communication between students with autism and non-disabled students to understand the challenges faced by peers with disabilities. For this, a little classroom preparation is needed, which the teacher might use simulations such as they can try tasks with one hand behind the back which can help non-disabled students to understand their peers with disabilities. These unusual responses to sensory experiences might be resistance to the environmental change. U.S. Department of Education (n.d.) says in section 300.8 that characteristics of individuals with autism are often associated with engagement in repetitive activities and stereotyped movements. If all affect a child's educational performance adversely, then autism does not apply to this because the child has an emotional disturbance. To meet their emotional disturbances, *social interaction and collaboration are needed*. To maintain social interaction support, group work areas should be scaffolded with clear, predictable tasks and choice boards for communication. These areas foster peer collaboration through social stories and turn-taking activities. This type of design will ensure that each element in the classroom supports communication, sensory management, and social interaction, which are based on best practices from research on autism intervention.

Methodology.

There are some key components for developing this learning environment, such as creating an inclusive classroom where there are students with autism. This study will focus on several components to address the challenges that people with ASD generally suffer from, as mentioned in the literature review. These components will be offered as part of personal development for teacher preparation students. Assuming pre-service teacher training curricula do

not include hands-on instruction on how to best accommodate individuals with disabilities, particularly ASD-related needs, the personal development environment would be a valuable addition to a module on disabilities. In the discussion section of this paper, the key components comprise visual supports, sensory-friendly spaces, collaborative learning, and behavioral strategies. The created PD modules can be of assistance for literacy development, academic excellence, and social improvement for people with various learning and developmental disabilities in inclusive classrooms.

This paper will be based on a set of foundational research to guide this design. Of course, preliminary research involves using and scrutinizing pedagogical theories that are related to universal design for learning (UDL) to ensure accessibility for all students. Concerning the key ideas for this design, here are several of those ideas for how the current learning environment design builds on. They are Applied Behavior Analysis (ABA), Universal Design for Learning (UDL), and Scaffolding Social Interaction. Applied Behavior Analysis (ABA) uses structured reward-based systems to reinforce positive behaviors and participation in learning tasks. Universal Design for Learning (UDL) ensures that classroom design and curriculum materials are accessible to all learners, including those with autism, through adaptable and flexible teaching methods. Scaffolding Social Interaction means using peer collaboration and structured turn-taking activities to build social competence. The next steps will be to develop the specific curriculum material or activities that, customized with these design ideas, are tailored to learners with ASD. These foundational readings and theories will build a structured design plan that can be applied in a real classroom setting or a professional development workshop.

This paper develops a learning environment for a 4th-grade EFL lesson using visual supports, sensory-friendly spaces, collaborative learning, and behavioral strategies to make the classroom inclusive for students with autism.

Analysis.

Instructional Design with Intervention Description

Designing curriculum materials or activities for children with autism requires a focus on structure, sensory support, visual aids, and flexibility to meet UDL requirements. Here is a set of classroom activities designed for a 4th grade EFL lesson “Reading Literature: Aesop’s fables”. The activities offered for this lesson plan are not only used for EFL classes but also for other subjects, making them universally adaptable, and this specificity is a main core for a Professional Development (PD) workshop for PCK. Here are the lesson plan activities for “*Reading Literature: Aesop’s fables*” aligning with UDL principles, which can be effective curriculum material enhanced with UDL components.

Title: Aesop’s Fables

Grade Level: 3rd Grade- UDL implementation

Subject: English (EFL)/Reading Literature (RL)

- MULTIPLE MEANS OF REPRESENTATION:

To be more accessible for all learners, multiple forms of perception should be offered, to meet diverse students’ needs who learn by seeing, hearing, touching, tasting and feeling. New vocabulary should be presented not only through verbal and singular visual examples, but they can be diverse making the lesson more accessible, achievable and flexible.

1. **Providing interactive slides** with visual supports asking students to pair fable character personalities with their images (e.g. "A slow, steady, and determined animal" with the image of a tortoise and "A fast, boastful, and overconfident animal" with the image of a hare). This is good for visual, tactile and those students who learn best by touching and they can benefit a lot by coming to the interactive board and do the matching activity by dragging and dropping. If the learning event becomes overwhelming, because individuals with autism can experience *sensory sensitivities*, such as self-stimulating behaviors (e.g. rocking, hand-flapping) they can be allowed to go to the cozy corner to retreat and feel secure.

0:04

✓ 0

Pair fable character personalities with their images: "A slow, steady, and determined animal."

◀ 2 of 2 ▶

0:03

✓ 0

Pair fable character personalities with their images: "A fast, boastful, and overconfident animal."

◀ 3 of 3 ▶

2. **Using graphic organizers** like a T-chart to separate examples ("The tortoise is a slow animal") and non-examples (The hare is not a boastful animal) in small groups. This activity is helpful for kinesthetic learners who percept by touching. For ASD students, this *visual support* works well because firstly, graphic organizers are visual using their sensory skills by touching and secondly, this group activity reinforces collaborative

learning and behavioral strategies, making the classroom inclusive. We can use soft and muted tones in the visuals to help ASD students to feel soothing colors.

3. **Bringing real-life objects** (e.g. household objects, fruit and vegetables) can be effective for learners who learn by touching to discuss what objects and food these fable characters use in their daily life. For ASD students, such *real objects can make transitions between activities smoother* and empower them to take the learning ownership, enabling them to complete tasks independently and build life skills.
4. **Bringing audio, video and text supports** (e.g. Youtube videos, short audio examples, and a Text-to-Speech tool) representing specific scenes of the fable and allowing students to choose any means to intake the information. This way of representation is efficient not only for auditory, visual and dyslexic learners, but also ASD students can find this way of information useful. *Communication* with children with ASD is more comfortable through such *assistive technologies* which are another accommodation for them to make the learning environment effective.

- **MULTIPLE MEANS OF ACTION AND EXPRESSION:**

1. **A Gallery Walk activity:** where learners mingle around the room and describe different pictures taken from different scenes of the fable in pairs. This would give kinesthetic and tactile learners an opportunity to move around the environment physically and engage in discussions with their peers. This *positive reinforcement* is applied to aid communication between students with autism and non-disabled students to understand the challenges faced by peers with disabilities. This structured peer collaboration and group work fosters inclusion while being scaffolded for individuals with ASD.
2. **Written description through small group discussions:** Groups are given different scenarios about the story prediction, and “what if - questions”. Students have to take their positions and write descriptive paragraphs about each fable character’s attitudes from different perspectives. This activity engages more students because those who have disorders with executive functioning or those who may struggle with speaking in front of the whole class can feel more comfortable in smaller groups. This *collaborative learning* component encourages social interaction through structured group work that fosters inclusion while ASD students being scaffolded. If their participation decreases and start getting anxious, they can go to *Sensory-Friendly Zones* which provide a calming environment for sensory regulation.
3. **Interactive social stories:** It is a kind of jigsaw reading that students have to do a group reading dividing the fable into chunks and then retell the fable in turn to their group. Since students differ in the ways that they can navigate a learning environment, UDL requires various learning tasks to enable students to show their mastery and potential. As pre-service teachers need to learn how to adapt standard teaching strategies to accommodate and deal with students' diverse sensory, cognitive, and social needs, using an *interactive social story education strategy* best supports students with Autism in mainstream classrooms.
4. **Role-play.** Role-playing appeals to diverse learning preferences. Small paper strips written different fable characters in are distributed to students of small groups to make sure that all students have one character assigned each. After few minutes of preparation

time, they can come to the board and play their roles. For ASD students, first the teacher can model how to play the role. Such *Scaffolding Social Interaction* means using group collaboration and structured turn-taking activities build social competence in such students.

- **MULTIPLE MEANS OF ENGAGEMENT:**

1. **Interactive storytelling:** where learners collaborate to start with one scene of the fable and continue with the next one in turn, until the assigned time is over, storytelling goes on in circles. Alternatively, group members can retell their part in different orders, and the other groups have to guess which part should come first, second and etc. In this storytelling activity, UDL principle of engagement is achieved because the social interaction and participation are guaranteed by adding more varied and interactive activities or storytelling that offer both choice and emotional support. ASD students can use their *choice boards for communication* which encourage independence by permitting them to communicate their preferences through visuals.
2. **Multiple perspective defense:** the teacher prepares and shares a list of multiple perspectives defense topics (e.g. “Compare the tortoise’s slow-and-steady persistence/hare’s overconfidence/the moral of the fable/humility of the tortoise/ hare’s procrastination, etc.”) to choose gives the learners *a chance of autonomy* to select the themes they are keen on discussing and comfortable to work on. While cooperating, individuals feel a low-stress learning event and they feel safe to regulate themselves. Since they have zero tension, they feel secure and enjoyable where they can easily manage their emotions and self-paced learning, owning and being responsible for their learning. Working with classmates assists learners stay motivated and reinforces the value of their contributions. Furthermore, *peer interactions* encourage students by a sense of community.
3. **Using assistive technology:** In addition to text-to-speech software for reading and verbal challenges, teacher can also bring digital tools like Canva and PowerPoint for creating visuals. Students can be asked to work in their small groups and create visuals imagining themselves as the tortoise or the hare in the fable incorporating their daily routines at school. While a buddy system helps students to brainstorm and create visuals, structured turn-takings while presenting assist them practice their oral presentation skills. If ASD students feel overwhelmed during group discussions, they can use *a quiet zone with noise-canceling headphones and dimmed lighting*.
4. **Sentence starters to help students initiate their ideas:** Students can be given sentence strips to reflect on their personal experiences or texts (“I connected with...because”, “One part I found surprising was...because” etc.), to share their opinions and interpretations (“One possible interpretation is...because...”, “I noticed...and think it means...” etc.). These starters encourage students to build on ideas, make connections, and articulate their thoughts with confidence. If this is done in pairs, reciprocal teaching would be specific to divergent learners of ASD by creating more accessible and engaging classrooms. This could enable students with ASD to actively take part in learning with their peers.

Designing curriculum materials or activities for children with autism requires a focus on structure, sensory support, visual aids, and flexibility to meet UDL requirements. Here is a set of classroom activities for a Professional Development (PD) workshop for PCK, which can be universally applicable across subjects:

1. Structured Visual Schedules.
 - Objective: Teaching children with autism how to follow routines and manage transitions.
 - Activity: Create individual visual schedules for each child using images or icons representing daily activities such as snack time, circle time or recess.
 - Materials: Laminated Images and pocket charts.
 - Implementation: Each child moves or marks the icon of the activity they are currently engage in. teachers can demonstrate how to use the schedule in a predictable sequence.
 - PD Workshop: Educators will learn to create and implement visual schedules customized with students with autism. They will also discuss the importance of predictability in reducing anxiety and enhancing engagement for children with ASD.

Nonfiction Visual Schedule

Arrival		7:30 - 7:40
Morning Bins		7:40 - 8:00
Reader's Workshop		8:00 - 8:40
Literacy Centers		8:40 - 9:20
Bathroom		9:20 - 9:40

<https://autismlittlelearners.com/visual-schedules/>

2. Sensory-Friendly Zones.
 - Objective: Providing a calming environment for sensory regulation.
 - Activity: Create a “sensory corner” where a child with ASD can go, if he/she feels overwhelmed. It can include items like fidget toys, soft lighting, weighted blankets and noise-cancellation headphones.
 - Materials: Weighted items, textured items, dimmable lights.
 - Implementation: Allow students to use this space when they need a break and teach them how to ask for time in the sensory zone.
 - PD Workshop: Educators will learn how to set up a sensory-friendly zones within a

<https://www.amazon.com/s?k=autism+bundle>

classroom, understand different sensory processing challenges, and identify when a child might take advantage from using this sensory corner.

3. Interactive Social Stories.

- Objective: Supporting children with autism in understanding social situations and developing communication skills.
- Activity: Develop personalized social stories that describe general social contexts such as greeting a friend, sharing toys and taking turns. The stories will have to use simple language and illustrations.
- Materials: Custom-based books with pictures, visual cards.
- Implementation: Read the story to the class and follow up with the role-playing the scenarios to reinforce learning.
- PD Workshop: Educators will learn how to make up and use social stories to address individual needs of children with autism. They will also practice writing their own stories based on common classroom scenarios.

<https://www.behaviorplace.com/blog/visuals>

4. Sensory-Integrated Literacy Activities.

- Objective: Enhancing literacy skills through sensory activities.
- Activity: For a reading activity, use textured letters or letter tiles that students can trace with their fingers while sounding out letters or words.
- Materials: Textured letters, sandpaper letters, letter tiles.
- Implementation: teachers show how children can match the texture of letters to their sounds. Engage students in a hands-on spelling game using these tactile resources.
- PD Workshop: Educators will practice designing multisensory literacy lessons that involve touch, sight, and sound to enhance engagement and learning for children with ASD.

<https://www.autismparentingmagazine.com/write-social-stories/>

5. Choice Boards for Communication.

- Objective: Encourage independence by permitting children to communicate their preferences through visuals.
- Activity: Create choice boards that engage students to select activities or communicate needs such as choosing a snack, book, or sensory toys.
- Materials: Laminated cards representing various choices.
- Implementation: Inspire students to point to or hand over a card to communicate their choice, reinforcing their communication skills.
- PD Workshop: Educator will learn how to make choice boards to reinforce communication, stressing out the necessity for clear visuals and flexibility in making choice.

6. Collaborative Learning Centers with Scaffolds.

- Objective: Developing social interaction and collaboration in learning tasks.
- Activity: Create learning centers where children with autism work in pairs or small groups on tasks like puzzles, sorting games, or art activities. Use clear step-by-step visual instructions to scaffold each task.
- Materials: Visual task cards, manipulatives such as puzzles or matching cards.
- Implementation: teachers facilitate students through every task, depicting how to work together and support each other.
- PD Workshop: Teacher will investigate strategies for setting up collaborative activities that accommodate divergent learning needs. They will concentrate on scaffolding and supporting peer interactions.

7. Positive Reinforcement Systems

- Objective: Encourage positive behavior through structured reinforcement.
- Activity: Develop a token or sticker reward system where students earn tokens for completing tasks or exhibiting positive behaviors like raising their hands, sitting quietly and asking for break time.
- Materials: Sticker charts, tokens, small prizes.
- Implementation: Educators explain the reward system openly and consistently encourage it by tracking positive behavior and rewarding effort.
- PD Workshop: Teachers will discuss the role of positive reinforcement in engaging children with autism and practice creating individualized systems tailored to specific behavioral goals.

<https://www.amazon.com/s?k=autism+token>

Discussion

Regarding research strategies and reliability, the following ASD-related challenges have been matched with UDL components based on the previous research. The first component is using *visual supports*, which integrate visual schedules and symbols to help students with autism follow classroom routines and transitions. For instance, using the Picture Exchange Communication System (PECS) to facilitate communication. The second crucial component for developing such a learning environment is using *sensory-friendly spaces* and *designing sensory regulation areas* within the classroom, such as quiet zones or sensory corners that students can use when they feel overwhelmed. They might find themselves in these quiet and comfortable zones, specifically lit with unsharpened lights. The next component is *collaborative learning*, encouraging social interaction in communications through structured peer collaboration and group work that fosters inclusion while being scaffolded to individual needs. Here, special education teacher, the main teacher, speech therapist, and ABA specialists also consider it to be participants of this collaboration. The last key component to be used in this project to address the potential challenges of ASD that pre-service teacher-trainers might be less aware of is *behavioral strategies*. Positive reinforcement and behavioral management techniques to encourage engagement will reduce anxiety and increase participation in classroom activities.

Conclusion

In summary, this paper highlights the importance of preparing pre-service teachers to engage students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) in inclusive classroom settings. By applying strategies such as visual supports, sensory-friendly zones, collaborative learning, and positive reinforcement systems, educators can create environments that encourage participation, reduce anxiety, and foster social interaction among students with autism. The incorporation of theories like Universal Design for Learning (UDL) and Applied Behavior Analysis (ABA) into

EFL classes provides a framework for accommodating the diverse sensory, physical, and social needs of neurodiverse learners.

The implications of this project point out the significance of training educators not only to understand autism but also to be familiar with teaching practices that ensure inclusivity. Teachers well-equipped with Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) specific to divergent learners can create more accessible and engaging classrooms, enabling students with ASD to actively take part in learning with their peers. This approach moves beyond sheer accommodation for not only for ELA classes but also for those that are universally applicable for all subjects, and these accommodations can be implemented into an education system where all systems regardless of ability, can succeed.

To conclude, nurturing inclusive education for students with autism necessitates deliberate effort in teacher preparation and classroom design. By addressing the sensory, communication, and social needs of students with ASD, educators can contribute to a more equitable and supportive educational environment in all subjects in schools. This paper has highlighted the significance of inclusivity, finally aiming to ensure that students with diverse needs are not just present but engaged and valued members of the classroom environment.

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